

ENGINEERING PRACTICES FOR FUNCTIONALITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Engineering as a profession is a call to service by the society. Perhaps next to soldiers, engineers are the most patriotic professionals. However unlike soldiers they remain servants of society at all times and in all circumstances. Despite her role to the society, engineering profession seems not to be enjoying the respect that is due to it probably because of the failures associated with some engineering projects. This paper discusses the potentials of engineering education and practices in the country to provide functional and sustainable services to the society. The major identified factors to achieve this quality have been as the teaching materials and equipment; staff capabilities and Industrial exposure. Though student recruitment was not a prominent factor for both students and employers, but was the main factor for staff. It is therefore important that it is not ignored. Engineering Services in the Country depends on a number of factors, some of which are not determined by Engineers themselves. However, there is no doubt that the future will be bright or dim depending on whether or not there exists a right relationship between the engineer and the Public or Institution which he serves.

INTRODUCTION

Engineering practices and education in Nigeria has been going through some changes including the development of new engineering programmes, reorganization of course content, re-installation of equipment among others. However, the questions of concern have been – is the quality of engineering education meeting needs of stakeholders? Are employers satisfied with the training of engineering graduates? Are students equipped enough to stand tall in the world of competition?

A renowned Physicist, Sir John Cockroft said that “the capacity of science to advance the life of the so called new states depends, more than on any single factor these include the recognition by the Government of a state of the importance of science to its economy and a willingness to devote adequate resources to the advancement of science and technology (Williams, 1990). In Nigeria, these prerequisites are lacking. Day by day Governments continue to pay lip service to the recognition of technology as *a sine qua non* to our development. New Universities are springing up all over the place more as a political expediency than as a real desire to provide technological knowledge to the youths of this country. We establish these institutions and failed to either staff them adequately both with regard to number and quality of staff, nor are they properly equipped for the discipline they are established to impart. The available funds is spread thinly over a proliferation of Institutes of higher learning, rather than consolidate well established ones which naturally require more funds for their existence in the present circumstances of inflation in the country. The result is that the products have not the real foundation on which to build experience.

Universities and Polytechnics have become status symbols for our states in this country and therefore their establishments are highly politicized and the students are the pawns on the chessboard of politicized education. I hope we will not get to the stage where Governments will only recognize the degrees obtained in their own university in preference to all others, or that degrees will be awarded by the quota system in our universities

Engineering and Development

There has been a strong link between engineering and development, whenever any nation or world leader brags about his achievement; it is usually within the context of one engineering feat or the other. In modern days, the United Nations has established some indices of development. Olunloyo (2001) has linked these indices to engineering (Table 1)

Table 1.0 United Nations World Development Indicators

SN	Indicators	Linkage with Engineering		
		Direct	Indirect	Strong
1	Size of Economy			✓
2	Quality of Life	✓		
3	Population and Labour Force		✓	
4	Poverty		✓	
5	Distribution of Income or Consumption	✓		
6	Education			✓
7	Health			✓
8	Land Use and Agricultural Productivity	✓		
9	Water Use, deforestation and Protected Areas	✓		
10	Energy Use and Emissions	✓		
11	Growth of the Economy			✓
12	Structure o Output			✓
13	Structure of Demand		✓	
14	Central Government Finances			✓
15	Balance of Payment and International Reserves			✓
16	Private Sector Finance			✓
17	Role of Government in the Economy		✓	
18	Power and Transportation	✓		
19	Communication, Science and Information Technology	✓		
20	Global Trade	✓		
21	Aid and Financial Flow			✓

Sustainable Practices and Functionality

At the turn of 1990s, the United Nations through its various slogans adopted the slogan sustainable development. In other word, the world was called upon to embark on development that can be sustained. This slogan is more appropriate to a country like Nigeria where we love to embark on white elephant projects that can not be sustained.

Designing for Sustainability

If our Nigerian Engineers must meet their challenges in building the country, there must be a radical change to our engineering project planning activities. In planning the following factors must be taken into considerations

Designing in relation to Environment and services

The environmental requirements of modern buildings have a great influence on structural design. Some requirements are statutory, others arise from activities within the building or they may be directives of the client. Solar radiation is a major source of heat within a building especially in tropical climate. A good roof should be able to regulate the solar radiation into a building. The thermal coefficient of a roof (including the ceiling), should not be more than 0.35w/m²°C (Barry, 1984). Thermal movement of heating and steam pipes can impose heavy loads on anchorage points and at other points of intentional or accidental restraints. Such movement and loads must be integrated in the structure. One of the greatest specialties of human being is the ability to modify the surrounding environment. This is best expressed in the method of clothing and building technology. Buildings are the most elaborate form of behavioral thermoregulation as they provide safe and controlled environment for humans and animals. The relative magnitude and the interactions of air and radiant temperature, humidity and air velocity have been found to determine the degree of thermal comfort of man (Hardy, 1973). While it is easy to construct structures against precipitation and high winds, it is not easy to build a system, which provides low thermal stress.

It is therefore essential that building should be designed by integrating both the meteorological and physiological factors in order to produce pleasant and comfortable environments. The relative magnitude and the interactions of air and radiant temperature, humidity and air velocity have been found to determine the degree of thermal comfort of man (Olaleye, 2005). The apparent human environmental requirements are for light, good air, and warmth. If occupants of any building could not enjoy these requirements in a building, such building is termed sick. 'Sick' Buildings is a new expression for construction with physical properties affecting health.

Designing in relation to Structural design resources

The question of resources in labour and materials does not frequently arise in advance countries in sufficient degree to influence choice of structure. In developed countries, however, particularly in 'emergent' countries, inaccessible areas, or areas subject to extreme natural phenomena, the question of resources may be extremely relevant. Local building methods and materials are sometimes worthy of adoption, particularly when low cost buildings are to be erected. Experiments will indicate the most suitable materials and methods to be used, and these will vary from place to place- steel, concrete bricks and blocks.

Designing for Comfort

Our buildings must be designed for comfort in order to make them homely. Physiological comfort in man is determined by both meteorological and non-meteorological factors. Non-meteorological factors include age, sex, type of clothing, diet, metabolic rate, work type and emotional state amongst others. The meteorological controls of physiological comfort in man are temperature, humidity, wind speed and radiation. There are various bio-meteorological indices for measuring physiologic comfort but most of them are based on meteorological factors since non-meteorological factors are in general not quantifiable.

Effective Index Method

Using the effective temperature index, the diurnal and seasonal variations of physiologic comfort could be obtained to assist in designing a healthy building. The effective temperature index was actually derived based on laboratory experiments involving human beings and is approximated by the equation

$$E_T = 0.4 (T_d + T_w) + 15 \dots \dots \dots \text{Eqn. 1}$$

Where E_T is the Effective Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{F}$; T_d and T_w are the dry bulb and wet bulb temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{F}$ respectively. Studies revealed that an ET value of 66 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ (18.9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and below indicates uncomfortable condition arising from cold stress while ET value in excess of 78 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ (25.6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) indicates uncomfortable condition due heat stress. Values of ET between 66 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ and 78 $^{\circ}\text{F}$ therefore represent optimum physiological comfort. Studies indicate that uncomfortable conditions arising from heat stress are common in most parts of the country during most of the day particularly during the dry season. The only exception is Jos Plateau area which because of its elevation does not suffer from heat stress. On the other hand, Jos and many of the far northern cities suffer from cold stress at nights and early in the mornings particularly between November and March when the harmattan weather prevails. Kaduna has been found out to have the best all year round climate in terms of physiological comfort while both Maiduguri and Lokoja emerge as having the worst. Altitude plays an important role in determining the physiological comfort in Nigeria because of its moderating effect on temperature. The Jos – Kaduna zone which has the best physiological climate in the country is in an area of relatively high elevation. In contrast, the lowland areas of the Niger Benue valley in the middle belt are oppressively hot. The Northern zones suffer from extremes of temperature usually associated with such continental locations while the Southern zones consisting mostly of low lying lands is relatively hot and humid for most parts of the year.

Physio-climatic stress is known to reduce the mental and physical efficiency of man and therefore deserves to be studied. Such studies can form the basis for wise scheduling of leave period and holidays as well as fixing appropriate official working hours amongst others (Ayoade, 1994).

HEATING AND COOLING DEGREE-DAYS Method

One method employed for this is finding the heating and cooling degree –days. A heating degree-day is defined as a 1° departure of the daily mean temperature from a base of 18.3°C (65°F) towards a lower temperature (that is, when the average temperature of a day is below 18.3°C (65°F), its value is subtracted from the 18.3°C (65°F) base and the difference gives the number of heating degree-days), a cooling degree –days can also be based on the temperature-humidity index, in which case it is defined as a 1° departure from the daily average temperature-humidity index expressed in degrees Fahrenheit, above a base of 15.6°C (60°F). The temperature-humidity index is computed from the equation:

$$THI = 0.4 (T_d + T_w) + 15 \dots \dots \dots \text{Eqn. 2}$$

Where *THI* is the temperature-humidity index, *T_w* is the wet bulb temperature (°F) and *T_a* is the air temperature

Table 2 shows the heating and cooling degree-day for six stations in the zone, using the mean monthly temperature. The heating degree-days were calculated by finding the difference between the base temperature of 18.3°C (65°F) and the average monthly temperature whenever the latter was lower. From the table it can be seen that all the stations have zero heating degree-days. This is basically because West Africa is in the tropics and has high average temperatures throughout the year. The cooling degree-days show comparatively high values before the heavy rainy period, for example in Lagos between February and May, preceding the heavy rainfall.

TABLE 2 (a) HEATING DEGREE-DAYS

Location	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Lagos	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ibadan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ado Ekiti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Akure	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oshogbo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abeokuta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The Zeros emphasize the prevalence of constantly high temperature

(b): COOLING DEGREE-DAYS

Location	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Lagos	5	7	7	6	5	3	1	1	0	3	6	5
Ibadan	5	7	8	8	5	3	1	1	2	3	5	5
Ado Ekiti	6	7	7	8	8	6	3	3	4	5	6	6
Akure	4	7	12	15	14	9	5	4	5	7	6	3
Oshogbo	1	5	12	18	19	15	10	7	9	12	8	2
Abeokuta	7	11	13	12	8	5	4	3	3	5	8	5

(Temperatures in Fahrenheit)

Engineering Practice for Sustainability

If engineering services in the country is to be properly maintained, we need engineers, technicians, artisans, skilled and unskilled labour. Each of these categories of staff must be properly trained for the part he is expected to play in the establishment. The Engineer is the high level manpower, the technician is the middle level manpower and the artisans – skilled unskilled labour are the junior level manpower. The accepted norm in engineering practice all over the world is that in order to get full value from one professional engineer he will have to work with 4 to 6 engineering technicians. I have gone into these details to show that all our engineering services must have their full complement of staff consisting the high level, the middle level and the lower level or junior manpower to be truly effective. If this normal standard is not achieved, and everyone belongs to the high level manpower, then there will be the need to use high

level manpower, then there will be the need to use high level manpower to do middle level manpower job leading to under-utilization of high level manpower, and therefore a wastage of manpower.

Administrators Intrusion

Another draw back to the advancement of Nigeria is the continued subjection of the professionals to the Administrators. The much desired development in this country will be retarded unless the Engineers are given their rightful place in the scheme of things in the country. Administrative Officer who has not the foggiest idea of what the engineers are expected to do. I made that statement because some years ago a high functionary of one of our Governments was reported to have said that if he could have his way he would sack all the engineers in the service and give all the jobs to Consultants. But then who are the consultants? Are they not engineers, some of whom might have resigned their appointments from the Service to become consultants?

Engineering Maintenance

Another important aspect of engineering practices is the maintenance of our infrastructures. One of the chief areas that our country is failing is in its inability to maintain what it has built or constructed. We plunge from one grandiose and expensive scheme to another whilst the previous ones are left to go to rack and ruin due to lack of maintenance, examples abound all over the country; buildings, fountains, express ways, Universities and so on. None of them has been properly maintained. When large sums have been spent on building, sufficient provision for their maintenance has not been made. Over a period of years, under tropical conditions where paint and fabric quickly deteriorate, it has been suggested that a sum of as much as 5 percent of the capital cost of erecting a building should be made available each year for its maintenance. If we accept this figure, then for buildings costing ₦2000, 000 a sum of ₦ 100,000 will be required each year. Another way of expressing this is to say that for every Naira spent on buildings, an equal sum should be put into an endowment fund to provide an income for their maintenance and upkeep. I think that it may be possible to keep the cost of repairs and or redecoration a little below this sum, but allowing for grass-cutting, gardens, and road repairs the economy will not be great.

Engineering Education

A survey was conducted among students, staff and employers of University of Ibadan to evaluate which factors they considered more important. Using a prioritization matrix, industrial exposure and linkages; Teaching Material and equipments have been found to be the most critical factors for quality engineering education. These factors have been weighed and the values compared for the different stakeholders. To ensure continuous improvement in the quality of education at the department a proposed strategic mapping for improvement has been suggested. According to Ibrahim (1999) “there is a difficulty in defining quality of engineering education”, however, there is the need to describe results of this quality in terms of ability to satisfy the current and future needs of industry, mobility, and life-long commitment to learning (Pile et al, 2013).

Prioritization of Quality Factors

Having considered the various factors for Quality Management analysis and how they have affected the general performance of the department, the author have prioritized these factors using a matrix based on results from discussions and interview of different stakeholders. The results are shown below in Tables 3 and Table 4.

From the prioritization matrix Table 3, it was observed that the most important factor for quality engineering education according to student perspective Industrial Exposure and linkages (with priority rating of 24.7 percent) and Content of curriculum as the least important with 1.6 percent priority rating. The relative importance of the quality factors is reflected in the percentile weight ratings. The order of importance is as follows: Industrial Exposure (24.7 percent), Teaching Materials and Equipment (20.9 percent), Teaching Methodology (17.2 percent), Relevance of student research (17.2), Student Recruitment (10 percent), Staff Capabilities (8.7 percent), and Content of curriculum (1.6 percent).

The staff were of different opinion and felt the student recruited for engineering programs are very critical for producing quality and independent engineering graduate yielding a priority rating of 40.8 percent and the teaching methodology (with priority rating of 2.2 percent), the least important. The order of importance is as follows: Student Recruitment (40.8 percent), Teaching Materials and Equipment (27.5 percent), Staff Capabilities (23.3 percent), Relevance of student research (10.1), Industrial Exposure (2.5 percent), Content of curriculum (2.4 percent) and Teaching Methodology (2.2 percent).

According to employers, Teaching Materials and Equipment, Staff Capabilities and Content of curriculum are the most critical factors for an enhance quality engineering graduate with priority rating of 35, 17.6 and 17.0 percent respectively. The least important to them is Student recruitment with rating of 1.9 percent.

Analysis of Results

The result obtained above is an indication that different stakeholders value some factors more than others. The reason of the poor overall rating for content of curriculum could be explained by the fact that irrespective of the curriculum content, if the needed teaching materials and equipment are not available, no better output could be expected. The consistent appeal of students for industrial trips and places for attachment is not out of place since they see it as a critical factor for success in their engineering carrier. Student recruitment plays a major role in the delivering of quality education. It is important to note that in spite of the available modern teaching material and equipment at the Civil Engineering Department, the quality of graduate is still questionable. It is therefore not surprising it was the highest rated factor for the staff. However, some employers are of view that with right practical orientation using the right teaching materials and equipment any student could be turned into a useful engineering graduate.

Strategic Mapping for Continuous Improvement

Based on the result gathered and the corresponding discussions made, a strategic mapping for continuous improvement in the quality of engineering education has been developed. Competent and committed staff; Modern equipment; Advertisement programs to enhanced quality students; Relevant textbooks as well as an effective dialogue concerning quality education has been identified as the support for building this quality.

The main process of an enhance quality teaching could be achieved through a practically oriented curriculum, professional staff development to improve staff capabilities, partnership with industry, properly supervised student attachment and recruitment of good students.

These factors would in the long run ensure not only the result of qualified and independent engineering graduate but also a fulfilled staff and more importantly a satisfied and independent engineering graduate but also a fulfilled staff and more importantly a satisfied employed.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

To ensure an improvement in the quality of engineering education, all stakeholders must get on board. The major identified factors to achieve this quality have been as the teaching materials and equipment; staff capabilities and Industrial exposure. Though student recruitment was not a prominent factor for both students and employers, but was the main factor for staff. It is therefore important that it is not ignored. If the suggested strategic mapping is adopted then engineering will exalted in the country. Engineering Services in the Country depends on a number of factors, some of which are not determined by Engineers themselves. However, there is no doubt that the future will be bright or dim depending on whether or not there exists a right relationship between the engineer and the Public or Institution which he serves.

Table 3: Quality Factors Prioritization (Student Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	Teaching Materials and Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	Relevance of student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	1	0.1	1.7	1.6
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	1	0.2	1	10	22.2	20.9
Industrial Exposure	10	0.2		5	1	5	5	26.2	24.7
Teaching Methodology	10	1	0.2		1	1	5	18.2	17.2
Relevance of student research	5	5	1	1		1	5	18	17.0
Staff Capabilities	1	1	0.2	1	1		5	9.2	8.7
Student Recruitment	10	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1			10.6	10

Table 4: Success Factors Prioritization (Staff Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	Teaching Materials and Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	Relevance of student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	1	1	0.2	0.2	0.1	2.7	2.4
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	10	5	5	1	31.0	27.5
Industrial Exposure	1	0.2		0.2	0.2	1	0.2	2.8	2.5
Teaching Methodology	1	0.1	0.2		1	0.1	0.1	2.5	2.2
Relevance of student research	5	0.2	5	1		0.1	0.1	11.4	10.1
Staff Capabilities	5	0.2	1	10	10		0.1	26.3	23.3
Student Recruitment	10	1	5	10	10	10		46	40.8

Table 5: Success Factors Prioritization (Employers Perspective)

Quality Factors	of Content curriculum	Teaching Materials and Equipment	Industrial Exposure	Teaching Methodology	Relevance of student research	Staff Capabilities	Student recruitment	Total	Percentage (%)
Content of curriculum		0.2	1	0.2	10	1	5	17.4	17.0
Teaching Materials and Equipment	5		5	5	10	1	10	36.0	35.2
Industrial Exposure	1	0.2		5	1	0.2	5	12.4	12.1
Teaching Methodology	5	1	0.2		1	0.2	1	8.4	8.2
Relevance of student research	0.1	0.1	1	1		1	5	8.2	8.0
Staff Capabilities	1	1	5	5	1		5	18.0	17.6
Student Recruitment	0.2	0.1	0.2	1	0.2	0.2		1.9	1.9

1 Equally Important

5 Significantly More Important

10 Exceedingly More Important

1/5 Significantly Less Important

1/10 Exceedingly Less Important

Table 6: Quality factors comparison for different stakeholders

Quality Factors	Student Perspective	Student Perspective	Student Perspective	Overall (Total)
Content of curriculum	1.6	2.4	17.0	21
Teaching Materials and Equipment	20.9	27.5	35.2	83.6
Industrial Exposure and linkages	24.7	2.5	12.1	39.3
Teaching Methodology	17.2	2.2	8.2	27.6
Relevance of student research	17	10.1	8.0	35.1
Staff Capabilities	8.7	23.3	17.6	49.6
Student Recruitment	8.7	23.3	17.6	49.6

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